

**INTERNAL CURRICULUM SUPERVISION OF LIFE SKILLS
EDUCATION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS:
A CASE OF LUGARI SUB-COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract:

Internal curriculum supervisors (ICSs) have a vast of roles to play to enhance effective implementation of the school curriculum. This paper is a report of a study that was undertaken in the year 2014 in secondary schools in Lugari sub-county in Kenya. The purpose of this study was to investigate the roles of ICSs in the implementation of Life Skills Education (LSE). The research objectives were: To determine the frequency at which the ICSs oversaw the preparation of the professional documents by teachers of LSE; and to assess how often the ICSs undertook classroom observation on LSE lessons. The study was guided by the behavioural theory of leadership. It utilized a mixed method research methodology and a descriptive survey research design. The sample size for the study comprised of 203 respondents that included 19 Heads of Departments (HODs), 19 Principals and 165 teachers of LSE. The teachers of LSE were selected through systematic random sampling method while the Principals and HODs were purposively selected. The research instruments used were questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis. The results of the study showed that ICSs rarely approved professional documents for LSE. Moreover, ICSs rarely conducted classrooms observation to check how LSE was being implemented by teachers in the schools. The lack of regular supervision affected the implementation of LSE in public secondary schools in Lugari sub-county in Kenya. The study recommended that ICSs should sensitize the teachers of LSE to prepare the required professional documents. They should check and approve them as required to enhance instruction in LSE. In addition, there is need for ICSs to conduct regular classroom observation for LSE lessons to ensure effective implementation of the curriculum. The findings are useful to the

Ministry of Education (MOE) in Kenya to ascertain the level of supervision of LSE. It creates awareness to ICSs on how best they can supervise LSE.

Keywords: internal curriculum supervision, life skills education, curriculum implementation

1. Introduction

The importance of supervision in schools in Kenya can be traced back to the time of colonial government. Beecher report (1949) cited by Somerset (2007) recommended efficient supervision of schools. Ornstein and Hunkins (1993: 201) state that:

“The field of curriculum and instruction is directly related to the field of supervision. Once curriculum is created, it needs to be looked at and be supervised on how it is being delivered.”

The overall education policy of the government of Kenya is to achieve Education For All (EFA) (Ministry of Education [MOE], 2008). The priority is to ensure equitable access and improvement in quality and efficiency at all levels of education. Education for all and the provision of quality education are among the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Kenya Vision 2030 respectively. To ensure quality of education, certain bodies are set up by the government and stakeholders to monitor instructional activities in schools. Internal Curriculum Supervisors (ICSs) promote change and effectiveness in the teaching and learning process (Okumbe, 1999). In Kenya ICSs include school principals and head teachers and their deputies, Heads of Departments and Heads of subjects. Supervised learning in general has positive effects on student achievement in that it: Improves achievement of high aptitude learners, assists the teaching and learning of students with special needs, produces positive effects on attitude towards learning, improves students’ attitudes and motivation, improves students’ team work and helps develop higher order thinking skills (Okumbe, 1999; Olembo, Wanga & Karagu, 1992; Sifuna, 2005).

Life skills are psycho-social competences and abilities that help individuals to effectively deal with the demands and challenges of everyday life (Kenya Institute of Education [KIE], 2008). In Kenya, Life Skill Education (LSE) is a compulsory subject in the secondary school curriculum that was introduced in the year 2008 with an aim of equipping students and teachers with the adaptive and positive behaviour that would enable them deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday (Republic of Kenya [RoK], 2010). The introduction of LSE in Kenya was spurred up by the many challenges that the youths are facing because of the fast changing world (Rungu, 2008).

These challenges may be psychological, social, and economic compounded by various factors such as complex development changes during adolescence, lack of positive role models, negative influence by mass media, inadequate, inaccurate and unreliable sources of information (UNESCO, 2005).

When the psychological and social needs of learners are not met, they become mal-adjusted and the resultant behaviour could be drug abuse, early marriages, teenage pregnancies, indiscipline, school unrest, poor carrier choices, premarital sex, increased crime, violence, rape, incest, suicide, HIV and AIDS pandemic, poor academic performance and loss of valuable employment among others (KIE, 2002; Mutai, 2013; Lutomia & Sikolia, 2006). Supervision is a strategy for curriculum improvement. Therefore, effective supervision of instruction is important because it monitors whether teaching is going on or not. It also helps teachers adapt to changes concerned with the curriculum. It further assists teachers to translate themes learnt in classroom into practice and finally it motivates teachers to accomplish their instructional goals (Black, 1995). This study was initiated to find answers on the effectiveness of ICSs on the implementation of LSE in public secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County, Kakamega County in Kenya.

1.1 Problem Statement

The need to focus on Internal Curriculum Supervision (ICS) of LSE in this study was informed by the challenges facing young people in Lugari sub-county in particular. Mutai (2013) and Lugari Constituency Strategic Plan (2010-2015) highlighted the challenges that young people in the area were facing. These challenges include youth becoming culprits of sexual exploit material, early pregnancies, indiscipline, school unrest, premarital sex, HIV and AIDS pandemic, poor academic performance among others. MOE has spelt out clearly the roles of Internal Curriculum Supervisors (ICSs) and these roles are well known and documented. Among the roles include: Checking and approving teacher professional records, supervising classroom teaching and learning, giving direction to schools to offer approved and diversified curriculum in accordance to circularised guidelines from the MOE and supporting organisations. For these initiatives to succeed, supervision is critical. ICS allows for constant monitoring, evaluation and review of implementation of LSE in schools to ensure it attains its objectives.

The gap addressed in this study was between internal supervisory roles and the implementation of LSE. The study sought to examine the efforts the ICSs have put to enhance effective implementation of LSE in public secondary schools in Lugari sub-county.

1.2 Research Objectives

The objectives of this study were:

1. To determine the frequency at which the ICSs oversaw the preparation of the professional documents by teachers of LSE in public secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County.
2. To assess how often the ICSs undertook classroom observation during LSE lessons in public secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County.

1.3 Justification of the Study

Life Skills Education was introduced as a stopgap measure to the many challenges that youths are facing today. Currently, there have been many episodes of crime and violence in Kenya and this reveals that the youth still face these challenges despite the introduction of LSE as a compulsory subject in secondary schools. Where LSE is developed and practiced, it enhances the well-being of a society and promotes positive outlook and health behaviour. Internal curriculum supervision promotes change and effectiveness in the teaching and learning process.

Research further reveals that ineffective supervision can affect the attainment of the curriculum objectives. Therefore, ICSs should put pressure on the users to implement the curriculum as required (MOE Handbook for Inspection of Education Institution, 2002). Effective supervision of instruction is important because it monitors whether teaching is going on well or not. It also helps teachers adapt to changes in the curriculum.

1.4 Theoretical Framework

This study was based on the behavioural theory of leadership (Liu, 1984). This theory has been directed towards the supervisors and administrators as instructional leaders (Hopkins, 2001). This theory focuses on the principals and Heads of Departments who engage in instructional leadership behaviour. Liu describes instructional leadership as a concept consisting of direct and indirect behaviour that significantly affect instruction. The direct leadership activities involve staff development, teacher supervision and evaluation whereas indirect leadership behaviour involves instructional facilitation (Girvin, 2005). Teacher supervision and evaluation involves all staff members. The ICSs need to conference with individual teachers to review their instructional plans. Teacher supervisors should regularly monitor the teaching of LSE; check professional documents such as schemes of work, lesson plans, lesson notes, records of work covered and student's progress records.

Evaluation of teachers is meaningless if the teachers are not able to define with their supervisors the objectives for evaluation. Supervisors who strive to exhibit instruction leadership must be prepared to engage in a wide range of activities that

support the instruction priorities of the school. Behavioural theory of leadership suits this study because the theory summarizes the roles of the instructional leaders who are the ICSs (Liu, 1984; Hopkins, 2001; Girvin, 2005).

The study focused on the roles of the ICSs in relation to the implementation of LSE in public secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County. Explicitly, the study centred on investigating the roles performed by ICSs in as far as the supervision of professional documents, and classroom observations in the implementation of LSE in public secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County was concerned.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Life Skills Education

The conceptual basis for most of the life skills work undertaken by the United Nations and its partners is the World Health Organisation's (WHO) Skills for Health state that:

"Life skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. In particular, life skills are a group of psychosocial competencies and interpersonal skills that help people make informed decisions, solve problems, think critically and creatively, communicate effectively, build healthy relationships, empathise with others, and cope with and manage their lives in a healthy and productive manner."

(WHO, 2001:8)

World Education Forum in Senegal-Dakar in April 2000 resulted in a Dakar Framework for action 2000 which refers to Life Skills in Goal 3 (Opio, 2010). LSE are abilities which enable an individual develop adaptive and positive behaviour so as to effectively deal with challenges and demands of everyday life.

The main goals of the life skills approach is to enhance young people's ability to take responsibility for making choices, resisting negative pressure and avoiding risky behaviour. Where LSE is well developed and practiced, it enhances the well-being of a society and promotes positive outlook and healthy behaviour. WHO ten skills can be divided into three broad categories: (i) communication and interpersonal skills, (ii) decision-making and critical thinking skills, and (iii) coping and self- management skills. These skills are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Categories of Life Skills

Communication and Interpersonal Skills	Decision-Making and Critical Thinking Skills	Coping and Self- Management Skills
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpersonal Communication Skills • Negotiation/Refusal Skills • Empathy Building • Cooperation and Teamwork • Advocacy Skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision-Making/Problem-Solving Skills • Critical Thinking Skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills for Increasing Personal Confidence and Abilities to Assume Control, Take Responsibility, Make a Difference, or Bring About Change • Skills for Managing Feelings • Skills for Managing Stress

Source: WHO (2001; 9).

In 2004, UNESCO hosted a meeting of the Inter-Agency Working Group on Life Skills in EFA (UNESCO, 2004), which discussed the links between life skills, lifelong learning and sustainable human development, and identified the need for a life skills-based education conceptual framework (including monitoring). It was hoped that such a framework would help to integrate a range of divergent perspectives (Somerset, 2007). As an approach, it was agreed that life skills-based education should be cyclic, sustainable and should employ participatory methods. It was also agreed, as a matter of practicality, that manual skills should not be considered life skills. However, this separation of psycho-social skills from practical skills is neither straightforward nor universally accepted, as the following quote from UNESCO, 2005: 5) demonstrates:

Life skills (are) not a domain, or a subject, but cross-cutting applications of knowledge, values, attitudes and skills, which are important in the process of individual development and lifelong learning. They are not just a set of skills, nor are they equal to survival skills, livelihood skills, or vocational skills but part of these skills.

Life skills-based education can be understood as either a part of a general process which develops complete individuals (public schooling), or something which is defined by the specific issues it is applied to (HIV prevention, conflict mediation). The debate over whether life skills-based education is a process or something defined by application is now being held in South Asia. In assessing the delivery of life skills-based education in South Asia, it is clear that many of these global issues and concerns are relevant to this region (UNICEF, 2005). LSE is a concept that originated in thinking about training and education (Opio, 2010). This kind of education covers the skills and competencies that an individual needs for sustaining and enriching life and also the kind of behaviour-based learning that the individual needs for coping with predictable developmental tasks (Rungu, 2008).

The central reason for including LSE in school curriculum is that an interventional, preventive and developmental approach to equipping school children in the senior phase with coping skills will help them to deal effectively with predictable developmental tasks and an ever-changing world. Throughout the world, youths face many physiological, psychological, social and economic challenges. Since the majority of the youth are in the school system, LSE is designed to help them cope with these challenges.

2.2 Internal curriculum supervision and curriculum implementation process

The process of curriculum development and implementation must be supervised (Liu, 1984). Someone must monitor what is occurring and determine whether the actions are appropriate. Controlling tasks ensures that tasks are carried out effectively, observing and evaluating work through feedback. Ornstein and Hunkins (1998: 314) state that:

The word supervision is associated with instruction. Supervision of instruction is important especially at the level of implementation. During the implementation phase, not only the manner of teaching but also the content that is actually being addressed needs to be supervised as well. Supervisors provide direction and guidance and make sure teachers have the skills to carry out the change.

Black (1995) conceptualized supervision as directing. Directing is assigning jobs, providing instruction, giving training, coaching and counselling individuals. It is also listening to and working out the related problems of employees and adjusting grievances. Olembo, Wanga and Karagu (1992) differ with Black (1995) contention that ideally; supervision is not only concerned with overseeing, directing, conducting, regulating and controlling teachers and pupils. It also involves guiding and influencing teachers and pupils to strive towards desirable teaching and learning behaviour in order to achieve educational goals and objectives. This view is supported by Okumbe (1999). According to him supervision is an administrative activity whose strategy is to stimulate teachers towards greater pedagogy effectiveness and productivity. Olembo et al., (1992:30) observes that 'supervision is that phase of school administration which focuses primarily upon the achievement of the appropriate instructional expectation of educational systems'.

It is therefore clear that the ultimate aim of supervision is the improvement instruction. The concern is not on the teachers but on the teaching or pupils' learning. Supervisors carry out numerous responsibilities to enhance effective implementation (Hopkins, 2001). A few popular ways are classroom observation, demonstration teaching, supervisor-teacher conference, staff development meetings, and grand funding (Ornstein & Hunkins, 1998). This study looked at the head teachers and HODs as the ICSs directly in charge of the implementation of LSE curriculum. According to the teacher handbook (2010), principals as an internal curriculum supervisors give

directions to the school. They offer a suitable approved and diversified curriculum in accordance to circularized guideline from the Ministry of Education and supporting organizations. The principals oversee teachers' preparation of schemes of work and development of appropriate instructional materials especially teaching aids. They periodically check pupils' exercise books, assignments and continuous assessment scripts to ensure regular marking and systematic use of guiding learning. They visit, observe and keep a record of learning sessions in classrooms. They create an environment for staff training and development such as orientation and induction; facilitate teacher course, seminars, workshops, conferences and staff clinics among others. In addition, they facilitate acquisition of equipment and materials in the school, they co-ordinate the supervision, motivate and appraise staff (KIE, 2002).

The HOD as an internal curriculum supervisor is a pivotal figure in the success of a school (Thobega & Miller, 2008). He/she is the chief professional in the subject area and is expected to set a positive, enthusiastic lead and to be an example of the practices to be followed by the members of the department. HOD's are directly responsible for the standard of teaching and the quality of learning that takes place in their subjects and are answerable to the head for this. They keep abreast of new curriculum thinking, teaching methods, examinations, syllabuses, textbooks and other resources and ensure that relevant information is communicated to members of the department and acted upon. They also have to support the head teachers in implementing performance management. They should observe the members of the department as they conduct the lessons from time to time. This is important in order to establish the dormant members of the department in the school. They also establish and revise the written aims, objectives, syllabuses and schemes of work for the departments (Thobega & Miller, 2008; Hopkins, 2001).

HODs have to work closely with the special needs in the department to ensure all students have equal access to the curriculum (Okumbe, 1999). They have also to identify strengths and areas of development with colleagues, providing outlets for strengths and offer guidance and training for development areas so that teachers within the department continue to improve their professional skills. They have a role to set high standards of work in their subject areas and to ensure that the department is working to those standards. They have to review examination results, identify strengths and areas for development in the department and assess if the performance in schools is improving or declining. By this they promote enthusiasm, openness to new ideas, commitment and a happy homogenous departmental team. They assist with the selection of teaching staff for their department after which they allocate staff to classes and pupils to teaching groups. This helps to ensure that teachers and learners are supported (KIE, 2002).

In consultation with the Deputy Head teachers/principals, HODs draw up a departmental framework policy within the schools' guidelines and ensure these are implemented by all members of the department by regular monitoring and evaluation. They manage the allocated capitation to ensure maximum pupil progress is attained, they keep the principal fully informed of the departmental developments, projects for the future and revise, monitor and evaluate departmental development plans annually. They also provide such reports on their departments as may be required by the government or the Head teacher, they establish inventories of all books and equipment held by the department to institute an annual stock check and to ensure that lists of resources are available to members of the department. This helps to contribute to the formulation and to co-operate in the implementation of school policies (Okumbe, 1999).

Having looked at the roles of the principal and the HODs as ICSs, it is evident that the main aim of supervision is to improve the teaching and learning process. As instructional leaders, ICSs are expected to possess a superior knowledge about curriculum and instruction, provide expert leadership in all areas of the school programme (Liu, 1984; Hopkins, 2001). For effective implementation of LSE, ICSs should take up their responsibility since their roles are well known and documented. The question addressed in this study was: How effective were the in ICSs in the supervision of LSE curriculum?

2.3 Planning for Instructions by Teachers

The ICSs are responsible for the quality of teaching in schools. Consequently, it is in the supervisor interest to see that records are kept which help the staff to do the job well (Farrant, 1980). Otunga, Odero and Barasa (2011) remark that instructional documents are important tools of instruction because they help the teacher to effectively and appropriately plan for and carry out instruction. Professional documents include the syllabus, scheme of work, lesson plans, records of work covered and students' progress records.

Planning is a vital role in implementation of teaching. Planning enables the teacher to sub-divide the content into manageable units (Otunga, et al., 2011). The ICSs are served with the responsibility of availing the LSE syllabus to the respective teachers and should ensure that they are in use. The syllabus is a document that gives the objectives for teaching and learning, an outline of the content, the sequence to be followed in a given knowledge area, it provides information on the preferred teaching material, methodology, evaluation or assessment procedure (Farrant 1980; Otunga et. al., 2011).

Schemes of work are also very important for any subject teacher. Since they are a teacher's plan of work from the syllabus, they show what is to be covered within a specific period of time (MOE, 2008). They must give a suggested allocation of time for

the teaching of each section of the syllabus and perhaps give recommended text books. Schemes of work make teaching both systematic and orderly since they ensure that topics in the syllabus are taught in an orderly manner (Farrant, 1980; Nasibi, 2003). Internal curriculum supervisors should check and approve the teachers' schemes of work to facilitate effective teaching and learning of LSE.

Lesson plans on the other hand are prepared by the teacher before instruction and used during the actual instructional process in order to have efficient and effective teaching and learning (Otunga et al., 2011; Farrant, 1980; Nasibi, 2003). Teachers of LSE are required to prepare lesson plans for effective teaching/learning and the lesson plans should be certified by the ICSs. The lesson plans enable the teachers to be familiar with the teaching content and to visualize the best way of covering it. Lesson plans give the teachers security and confidence from having a well-developed and organized framework for the day's instructions.

Records of work covered are other documents that need to be kept by the subject teachers. Otunga et al., (2011) assert that the record of work covered helps the teacher to keep a clear account of the areas of the syllabus that are covered. The internal curriculum supervisors should check to ensure that LSE teachers keep the record of work covered book in order for them to record what they have taught.

To summarize, professional documents are very important for any teacher to facilitate effective and efficient teaching and learning. These documents are prepared by the teacher teaching a particular subject or course under the supervision of the internal curriculum supervisors for effective implementation of the curriculum. This study sought to determine the frequency to which ICSs oversaw the preparation of professional documents by the teachers of LSE in public secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County.

2.4 Classroom Observation and school improvement

Fullan (1992) revealed that school improvement can be realized when the teachers and educational administrators frequently observe each other teaching and provide each other with useful evaluation of teaching. Supervisors provide direction and guidance and make sure teachers have the skills to carry out the change. Those charged with supervising the school curriculum are responsible for overseeing or directing the work of others. The recent concept in instructional supervision is clinical supervision. Okumbe (1999: 176) refer to clinical supervision as "*The rational and practice designed to improve the teacher classroom performance.*"

The data of clinical supervision is obtained from the events which take place in the classroom. The relationship between the teacher and the supervisor in clinical supervision is aimed at improving the teachers learning behaviour. Internal curriculum

supervision should strive at improving all factors involved in pupils' learning to enhance the teaching and learning of LSE. Administrative support is provided through supervision by school administrators. According to Olembo et al., (1992), supervisory roles include working closely with teachers to establish their problems and need of the students, building a strong group morale and securing effective team work among teachers and providing assistance to teachers so as to help them develop greater competence. The supervisors can also assist beginning teachers to translate the theories learnt in college into class room practices. They work with teachers to identify and analyse learning difficulties and help in planning effective remedy instruction. Thobega and Miller (2008) emphasize the role of supervision in providing motivation, a feeling of self-respect and high morale which leads to increased competence on the job and greater job satisfaction. This study assessed the extent to which ICSs undertook classroom observation during LSE lessons in public secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County.

3. Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in Lugari Sub-County in Kakamega County of Nzoia region. A mixed method research was utilized. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The target population of the study included all 290 teachers, 19 HODs of Guidance and Counselling departments and 19 Principals. The sample size comprised of 203 respondents. Out of these were, 19 HODs, 19 Principals and 165 teachers of LSE. The study utilized questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis to collect data. Questionnaires were administered to teachers of LSE and HODs of Guidance and Counselling departments while interviews were prepared for the principals. Teachers' professional documents were analysed to determine their availability and use. Validity of questionnaires and interview schedules was determined through consulting and discussing with the thesis supervisors and Masters of Education students in the Department of Curriculum, Instruction and Educational Media in Moi University. The reliability of the questionnaires and interview schedule was improved through test re-test method. Quantitative data was done using descriptive statistics while qualitative data was analysed using thematic approach.

4. Research Results

4.1 Frequency to which ICSs oversaw the preparation of professional documents by teachers of LSE

The first research objective was to investigate the frequency to which ICSs oversaw the preparation of professional documents by teachers of LSE in their schools. This was

based on the aspects of objectives, content, teaching methods and methods of evaluation. Teachers' responses are given in Table 2. Liu (1984) points out that the principal as a supervisor has the major responsibility of communicating the overall school goals to the teachers as part of the evaluation process and this happens through overseeing the preparation of the professional documents for teachers of LSE. The teachers of LSE were asked to indicate the extent to which ICSs oversaw the preparation of their professional documents. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Frequency to which ICS's oversaw the preparation of the professional documents of teachers of LSE

Aspect of LSE	Very often	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
i. Objectives	4(2.8%)	44(30.6%)	42(29.2%)	54(37.5%)	144(100.0%)
ii. Content	6(4.2%)	44(30.6%)	46(31.9%)	48(33.3%)	144(100.0%)
iii. Teaching methods	4(2.8%)	36(25.0%)	42(29.2%)	62(43.1%)	144(100.0%)
iv. Method of evaluation	0(0.0%)	30(20.8%)	44(30.6%)	70(48.6%)	144(100.0%)

The findings revealed that 54 (37.5%) of ICSs did not guide teachers on the objectives of LSE, 42 (29.9%) conducted it on rare basis, 44 (30.6%) guided teachers often while only 4 (2.8%) always guided teachers on teaching methods. This implies that ICSs do not always guide teachers of LSE on the objectives of the LSE curriculum. Furthermore, 48 (33.3%) said that ICSs do not direct them on LSE content, but 46 (31.9%) pointed out that they are directed on rare occasions, 44 (30.6%) noted that they are often guided while 6 (4.2%) said that they are regularly guided on the content of LSE curriculum. Regarding the LSE teaching methods, only 4 (2.8%) were regularly guided, 36 (25%) were often guided by ICSs, 42 (29.2%) were rarely directed on the teaching methods and 62 (43.1%) noted that their ICSs did not guide them on the methods that are appropriate for teaching LSE. On the method of evaluation, none (0%) of ICSs directed teachers on regular basis, 30 (20.8%) often guided teachers, 44 (30.6%) said that they are rarely guided while 70 (48.6%) said that they have never been guided on the methods of evaluating LSE curriculum.

It was clear that the guidance of ICSs to teachers on different aspects of LSE was conducted on irregular basis in majority of secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County. Maranya (2001) also found out that head teachers rarely oversaw the preparation of teaching materials for implementation of secondary schools curriculum in schools in Machakos District in Kenya. This provides little for direct instructional leadership as Liu (1984) found out that head teachers who talk with teachers and supervise their strengths and weaknesses in the process of teaching and learning foster teacher proficiency. Therefore, ICS's need a close relationship with teachers in order to supervise the curriculum and monitor students' progress in LSE.

4.2 Heads of Departments roles in directing teachers of LSE

The Heads of Departments (HODs) were requested to give their opinion on how frequent they guided teachers of LSE on objectives, content, teaching methods and methods of evaluation of LSE. The findings are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Heads of Departments roles in directing teachers of LSE

Frequency of directing	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
i. Objectives	2(10.5%)	8(42.1%)	9(47.4%)	19(100.0%)
ii. Content	4(21.1%)	5(26.3%)	10(52.6%)	19(100.0%)
iii. Teaching methods	2(10.5%)	6(31.6%)	11(57.9%)	19(100.0%)
iv. Method of evaluation	2(10.5%)	6(31.6%)	11(57.9%)	19(100.0%)

It was evident that 9 (47.4%) of the Heads of Departments (HODs) had never guided the teachers on objectives of LSE, 10 (52.6%) said that they did not guide them on the content of LSE, 11 (57.9%) said that they did not guide teachers on the teaching methods while 11 (57.9%) indicated that they did not direct teachers on the methods of evaluating LSE in schools. This implies that the HODs did not direct LSE teachers on different aspects of the subject. The results also indicated that the HODs rarely evaluated the teaching of LSE, coordinated the LSE curriculum, instructional time nor observed the LSE teaching. The duties of the HODs include evaluating teaching, coordinating curriculum programs, protecting instructional time, observing teachers, providing incentive to teachers, promoting professional development and providing incentive learning (Okumbe, 1999).

4.3 Approval of Professional Documents in LSE by the ICSs

Professional documents are important tools of instruction because they help teachers to plan and carry out instruction (Otunga et al., 2011). As part of supervision in schools, approval of key professional documents such as schemes of work, lesson plans, lesson notes, records of work covered and students' progress records on a scale of four: 1- Never, 2-Rarely, 3- Often and 4-Very often was suggested. Descriptive results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Approval of Professional Documents in LSE by ICSs

Professional Documents	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
i. Records of work covered	144	1.00	4.00	1.7917	.99205
ii. Students' progress records	144	1.00	4.00	1.7500	.98938
iii. Lesson notes	144	1.00	3.00	1.7083	.77709
iv. Schemes of work	144	1.00	3.00	1.6667	.78722
v. Lesson plans	144	1.00	4.00	1.6528	.80770
Valid N (List wise)	144	1	4	1.7139	0.8707

The results of the study revealed that ICSs in the secondary schools rarely (M=1.71 and SD=0.87) approved professional documents on LSE teaching in secondary schools. The ICSs approved records of worked covered more (M=1.79 and SD=0.9) as compared to lesson plans which was the least (M=1.65 and SD=0.87) approved instructional document in schools. The results imply that ICSs do not regularly approve professional documents in LSE. The results of Musungu and Nasongo's (2008) survey in Vihiga County schools found that effective supervision by the head teachers would result to good performance. The practice by ICSs of not approving professional documents is against the recommendation by Otunga et al., (2011) who said that ICSs should check professional documents to ensure teachers keep records of what was covered in classroom teaching.

4.4 Heads of Departments' responses on approval of professional documents in LSE

It was also important for the study to look at the frequency to which the Heads of Departments (HODs) approved various professional documents: Schemes of work, lesson plans, lesson notes, records of work covered and students' progress records in the schools. The analysis of results is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Heads of Departments' responses on approval of professional documents in LSE

Professional Documents	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
i. Schemes of work	1(5.3%)	4(21.1%)	14(73.7%)	19(100.0%)
ii. Lesson plan	0(0.0%)	7(36.8%)	12(63.2%)	19(100.0%)
iii. Lesson notes	0(0.0%)	10(52.6%)	9(47.4%)	19(100.0%)
iv. Records of work covered	0(0.0%)	7(36.8%)	12(63.2%)	19(100.0%)
v. Students' progress records	0(0.0%)	7(36.8%)	12(63.2%)	19(100.0%)

The results of the study showed that the Heads of Departments (HODs) in the secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County did not approve LSE documents. The results further showed that the HODs rarely approved lesson notes 10 (52.6%) for LSE in schools. Similarly majority of the head teachers interviewed revealed that they did not approve professional documents for LSE in the schools. The results differed with behavioural theory of leadership. Liu (1984) observe that the approval of professional documents as part supervision of curriculum needs to be systematically carried out by the HODs. However, this seems to be different in the secondary schools Lugari Sub-County.

4.5 ICSs and Classroom Observation

The second research objective investigated the frequency at which internal curriculum supervisors undertook classroom observation during LSE lessons. Supervision of

teachers is one of the responsibilities delegated to the head teachers by the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) in Kenya. An instructional leader is responsible for the overall direction and goals of the school (Hopkins, 2001). Head teachers are the overall supervisors of all academic and administrative activities in the school, and the ones responsible for improving and maintaining high teaching and learning standards in the school (Liu, 1984). Fullan (1992) argues that effective curriculum implementation can be realised when head teachers frequently conduct classroom observation regularly and evaluate teaching and learning process in schools. Three statements were framed on the degree to which ICSs conducted classroom observations and the teachers were asked to give their opinion on a Likert scale of five: 1–Strongly Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Undecided, 4 – Agree and 5 – Strongly Agree on the extent to which head teachers conducted supervision on LSE. The results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Teachers’ responses on classroom observation as undertaken by ICSs

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
i. The internal curriculum supervisors check the students exercise books	144	1.00	5.00	2.6806	1.36171
ii. The internal curriculum supervisor advices me on the proper use of the instructional material	144	1.00	5.00	2.6250	1.36802
iii. The internal curriculum supervisors regularly observe me as i teach LSE	144	1.00	5.00	2.3750	1.35769
Valid N (List wise)	144	1	5	2.5602	1.36247

The results of the study (Table 6) showed that respondents had mixed perceptions (M=2.56 and SD=1.36) on the ICSs and classroom observation in LSE in the secondary schools. The respondents seem to disagree (M=2.37 and SD=1.35) that ICSs regularly observed them as they conduct LSE in the classrooms. This is contrary to behavioural theory of leadership tenets that argue that ICSs need to ensure the enforcement of the teaching period for teachers to use instructional time effectively. It will encourage teachers and students to be involved in school activities (Liu, 1984). The findings of the study further showed that LSE teachers were not advised by ICSs on proper use of instructional materials and their role of checking students’ exercise books. This could be because all (100%) of head teachers said that they did not conduct classroom observations in LSE.

Maranya (2001) cautioned that failure of ICSs to conduct classroom observation result to failure in the implementation of curriculum. This therefore shows that ICSs non-commitment to conduct classroom observation has resulted to partial implementation of LSE. An observation by the researcher showed that LSE curriculum was accommodated in the timetables in some schools but there was no emphasis put in the teaching of life skills but instead examinable subjects were taught during LSE

lessons. This showed that ICSs did not oversee the implementation of LSE curriculum in schools. The findings correspond to Kipng'etich's (2008) study in secondary schools in Bomet Sub-County that realised that Physical Education (PE) subject lessons paved way for teaching of examinable subjects. This is different from what is happening in Malawi where Chirwa (2009) found out that most of the principals supported the teaching of LSE by ensuring availability of resources and encouraging teachers treat LSE as seriously as they treat other subjects.

4.6 Heads of Departments' roles in supervision of LSE Curriculum

Supervision is an act by the ICSs of managing, overseeing and giving direction to teachers (Liu, 1984). HODs were asked to indicate the extent to which they conducted classroom observation on LSE for maintenance of quality control in classroom on a Likert scale of five: 1–Never, 2–Seldom, 3–Rarely, 4–Occasionally and 5–Always. Summary of analysis is given in Table 7.

Table 7: Heads of Departments' roles in supervision of LSE Curriculum

Roles	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
i. I regularly observe LSE teachers as they teach	19	1.00	4.00	2.2632	1.40800
ii. The internal curriculum supervisors check the students exercise books	19	1.00	4.00	2.1053	1.28646
iii. The internal curriculum supervisor LSE teachers on the proper use of the instructional material	19	1.00	4.00	2.0000	1.10554
Valid N (List wise)	19				

The results of the study show that the HODs seldom ($M=2.26$ and $SD=1.4$) observed the teaching of LSE, they also hardly ever checked students' exercise books ($M=2.1$ and $SD=1.2$) and they rarely ($M=2.0$ and $SD=1.1$) supervised teachers on the proper use of instructional materials. The results corresponded with earlier response by the teachers of LSE that showed that LSE teaching was rarely supervised by ICSs. The results are consistent with Opio's (2010) findings that showed that there was less involvement of other stakeholders such as counsellors in supervision of life skills programmes in primary schools in Uganda. Chirwa (2009) also found out that disparities arose in supervision between urban and rural schools in LSE. Chirwa found out that urban schools received frequent supervision in the teaching of LSE, whereas rural schools did not receive supervision. The conduct of the HODs as internal curriculum supervisors in Lugari Sub-County is contrary to the expectations of instructional behavioural theory that states that they are responsible for supervising and evaluating teaching and learning of LSE. This can lead to non-achievement of the school goals since less time is taken to assess the teaching and learning of LSE in the classrooms (Liu, 1984). Maranya

(2001) adds that effective supervision will lead to effective curriculum implementation in secondary schools. In addition, researchers such as Teuzi (2009); Musungu & Nasongo (2008) and Syomwene (2003) argue that for achievement of curriculum goals in schools, regular class supervision is important.

4.7 Findings obtained from Document Analysis of Teachers' professional documents

The researcher study visited 19 secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County to examine the availability and utilisation of various LSE professional documents. The outcomes are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Approval of Teacher Professional Documents in LSE

Professional Documents	Status		Not available
	Approved	Not approved	
i) Schemes of work	2	0	17
ii) Lesson plan	0	0	19
iii) Lesson notes	0	7	12
iv) Record of work covered	0	0	19
v) Students progress records	0	0	19

The results show that only two (2) secondary schools had approved schemes of work for LSE while the rest (17) did not prepare. Further, lesson notes were found in seven (7) schools but they were not approved by ICSs while records of work covered, lesson plans and students' progress records were unavailable in all 19 secondary schools in Lugari Sub-county

5. Conclusions

The results of the study revealed that internal curriculum supervisors rarely approved or oversaw the preparation of professional documents for LSE. Head teachers and HODs said that they rarely or never approved the professional documents prepared by teachers of LSE in the secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County. These documents included records of work covered, students' progress records, schemes of work of and lesson notes. In addition, it was found out that the internal curriculum supervisors did not conduct classroom observation on LSE lessons in the secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County. This situation has great implications on the implementation of Life Skills Education curriculum in secondary schools in Lugari Sub-County.

6. Recommendations

In the light of the findings, this study recommended that ICSs should sensitize the teachers of LSE to prepare the required professional documents. They should check and approve them as required to enhance instruction in LSE in the schools. In addition, there is need for ICSs to conduct regular classroom observation for LSE lessons to ensure effective implementation of the curriculum.

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